

EARTHQUAKE SWARMS: RECOGNITION AND CHARACTERISTICS

Lyutikova Veronika Sergeevna¹,
Litovchenko Irina Nikolaevna²

¹*National Scientific Center for Seismological Observations and Research of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Almaty, Kazakhstan*
nikki.valo16@gmail.com, litovira@rambler.mail.com

Abstract. *This paper analyzes the current seismic activity of the Northern Tien Shan region and adjacent territories for the period from 2017 to 2025. An algorithm for identifying earthquake swarms is presented, and corresponding maps and diagrams are created based on its application. Physical and mathematical criteria used to identify earthquake swarms are described. It is concluded that earthquake swarms often precede strong earthquakes, the foci of which are formed in the earth's crust from structural inhomogeneities saturated with high-temperature masses, 1.5-2 years before the main event. The spatio-temporal distribution of earthquake swarms is displayed for the seismicity of the region under consideration for 2024-2025.*

Key words: seismicity, earthquake swarms, swarm recognition, physical and mathematical criteria, swarm mapping

1 Introduction

As part of the study of the modern seismic situation, using data for 2017-2025 as an example, earthquake swarms were studied [1]. For their identification, an algorithm developed by the authors was used [3, 4, 8, 14]. Earthquakes, as underground tremors and vibrations of the earth's surface caused by the displacement of tectonic plates, reflect the processes of geological development of the planet. Although the exact causes of earthquakes, including the nature of the occurrence of swarms, are not fully understood, they are believed to be associated with temperature changes in the bowels of the Earth [12]. Most earthquakes are localized near the boundaries of tectonic plates. Over the past two centuries, strong earthquakes have often occurred as a result of faults reaching the surface [12]. More than a million seismic events are recorded annually. Due to the increase in the number of observation points and the improvement of equipment, more and more earthquakes occurring in the depths of the Earth are recorded. If at the beginning of the 20th century about 40 earthquakes with a magnitude of $M \geq 7$ were registered, then in the 21st century about 4500 such events have been recorded over the decade. Earthquakes are classified by energy into strong, weak and microearthquakes. The terms "destructive" or "catastrophic" are applied to earthquakes of any strength if they lead to destruction and human casualties [12]. Earthquake swarms are characterized by impulsive appearance and disappearance in certain areas, as well as low energy indicators. They are often observed in areas of active volcanoes, geyser emission zones, as well as in plain and mountainous areas, although seismic activity is higher in coastal than in continental areas. Swarms of earthquakes of volcanic and tectonic origin have a similar nature - hydraulic shocks caused by the movement of magma through channels in the bowels of the Earth. A distinctive feature of volcanic swarms is the gradual decrease in the depth of earthquake foci, in contrast to tectonic swarms, where the depth usually remains constant, as shown by observations of volcanologists [13].

As a result of a hydraulic shock in the earth's crust, an unbalanced state of rocks in the impact zone occurs. The kinetic energy of the molecules' motion increases sharply, being distributed chaotically over their internal degrees of freedom, which causes significant tangential stresses and powerful shear deformations. The development of these deformations occurs extremely quickly, within about 10^{-7} seconds. High concentrations of dislocations are formed in the rocks of the mantle and the earth's crust, and the crystal lattices are crushed. During subsequent time intervals from 10^{-12} to 10^{-9} seconds, chemical bonds are broken, accompanied by a sharp increase in pressure, temperature, and density. This leads to the formation of excited molecular states, their subsequent dissociation, and possibly ionization [13]. After about 10^{-6} seconds, the wave source is "unloaded", but the irreversible processes that occurred as a result of the shock leave the impact zone heated. This contributes to further displacements in the rock mass, the formation of new faults and cracks, their overlapping, and, as a consequence, the repetition of hydraulic shocks and seismic wave swarms [13]. The power of a hydraulic shock depends on the size of

the faults and can be quite significant. The time and place of occurrence of subsequent hydraulic shocks are random, which makes short-term forecasting of tremors fundamentally impossible. A swarm of volcanic earthquakes clearly indicates the beginning of the movement of magmatic masses to the surface and the activation of volcanic activity. The mechanism of formation of an earthquake swarm serves as a convincing argument in favor of the insignificance of the role of elastic deformations in the processes leading to earthquakes [13]. To study and identify earthquake swarms, the authors of the work developed specialized software packages and algorithms. To identify earthquake swarms, physical and mathematical conditions applicable to the seismicity of the studied region were formulated [9, 10].

2.1 Initial data

2.1 Implementation of the recognition algorithm

The seismic activity of the Northern Tien Shan region and adjacent territories was used as the initial data for the study.

Objective of the study: Recognition of earthquake swarms in the seismic picture of the region. To achieve this goal, the earthquake catalog [1] and the graphical clustering method (GCM) [3, 4] were used. For the territory limited by coordinates 39-46°N and 70-85°E, earthquakes with a magnitude of $K \geq 7$ are typical in the period from 2017 to 2025, which is shown in Figure 1. An analysis of the general seismic activity of the region was carried out in order to identify earthquake swarms in it using the GCM algorithm [3, 4]. From the flow of seismic events (see Fig. 1), using certain criteria based on quantity, spatial distribution and time, seismic events that form earthquake swarms are identified and grouped.

1. It is assumed that earthquake swarms form 1.5-2 years before strong underground tremors that occur in the earth's crust due to structural inhomogeneities saturated with high-temperature materials.
2. The process of swarm formation can be considered as a form of spatial concentration of seismic events [4]. Some general qualitative and quantitative characteristics of earthquake groups with $K \geq 9$ ($M=2.8$) in the Northern Tien Shan are presented in [2, 3, 6-9]. 3. The radius of probable concentration of events was taken within 18-20 km, with 10% of earthquakes in the sample belonging to these groupings [2-4, 5-11]. 4. Stable clusters characterized by an angular size of no more than 20'-25' (corresponding to focal zones of earthquakes with a magnitude of 6-7 in the study area) are formed when the distance between events is no more than 10'. 5. Physical and mathematical patterns determining the formation of earthquake swarms and associated with their intensity (the number of events in a group) were revealed. 6. The probability of a random coincidence of three events within a radius of 10' is extremely small and can be ignored. This allows us to better understand the formation mechanism and clarify the criteria for identifying swarms. 7. Thus, the swarm recognition method based on the MGKI algorithm was successfully implemented to analyze the seismic activity of the Northern Tien Shan and adjacent areas in the period from 2017 to 2025.

Below are the criteria used to identify earthquake swarms.

1. Quantitative. A group of earthquakes is considered a swarm if it contains at least 3 events, with no restrictions on the maximum magnitude. For a more accurate description of the swarm, an additional physical and mathematical criterion is used.

2. Temporal. Swarms can exist from several minutes to months or even years. Therefore, they cannot be unambiguously characterized only by the number of events or duration.

3. Time interval between events. The physical and mathematical condition is the time interval between earthquakes in a swarm ($0 < t_{\text{swarm}} < 26$ days).

2.2 Results

The presented conditions and their numerical values provide a more accurate physical and mathematical dependence in recognizing earthquake swarms in the region under consideration and are of a universal nature. These criteria allow one to identify earthquake swarms and better understand their occurrence and development. Based on the developed physical and mathematical criteria, the distribution of earthquake swarms in the territory of the Northern Tien Shan and adjacent areas for 2017-2025 was identified and displayed on maps-schemes (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Seismicity map of the Northern Tien Shan region and adjacent territories for 2017-2025 with ($K > 7.0$) [1].

Fig. 2 Map-scheme of the spatial-temporal distribution of earthquake swarms for the period 2017-2025 (K - energy class, depth (km) - scale presented in different colors)

Figure 3 shows a schematic map of the spatio-temporal distribution of recognized earthquake swarms for 2024-2025.

Fig. 3 Map-scheme of recognized earthquake swarms in the Northern Tien Shan region and adjacent territories for 2024-2025

3 Conclusions

Analysis of the spatiotemporal distribution of recognized earthquake swarms in the study region (see Fig. 3) shows that in 2024-2025, most swarms are localized in the southern and southeastern parts of the region. Separate clusters of swarms are observed at coordinates 40-42° N, 78-79° E and in the southeastern part of the region at coordinates 40-42° N, 80.5-84° E, with a gradual shift to the northeast. In 2024-2025, earthquake swarms (see Fig. 3) are predominantly located east of the 77° E meridian.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the recognition, occurrence and mapping of earthquake swarms have been studied previously by many researchers, but there is still no single generally accepted understanding of them.

4 Acknowledgments

The authors thank the scientific director, Academician of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan Kurskeyev A.K. for scientific guidance and the staff of the SOME for the provided seismological data.

Literature

- [1] Earthquake Catalogue / Seismic Experimental and Methodological Expedition of the Republic of Kazakhstan [Electronic resource]: access mode - <http://some.kz/index.php?p=card&outlang=1&oid=9>
- [2] Kurskeyev A.K. Earthquakes and seismic safety of Kazakhstan Almaty. 2004. Evero. - 504 p.
- [3] I.N Litovchenko., V.S. Lyutikova Recognition of earthquake swarms // IX International Conference on Cognitive Sciences and AI. - Moscow, 2021. -pp.282-285.
- [4] V.S Lyutikova. Earthquake swarms as a reaction of energy-saturated structures of the earth's crust to the impact of astrophysical factors // World Congress of Engineers and Scientists "Energy of the Future: Innovative Scenarios and Methods for Their Implementation", WSEC-2017.-Astana, Kazakhstan,-V.4.-Almaty, 2017.-pp.328-331.
- [5] A.K Kurskeyev., K.K., Kolumbetova I.N Litovchenko., N.B Amirov., V.S Lyutikova. On the physical nature of earthquake magnitude // Modern methods of seismic hazard assessment and earthquake forecast for the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan (16.06.-18.06.2022). - Almaty, 2022.-pp.141-148.
- [6] I.N. Litovchenko Physical parameters of focal zones of strong earthquakes of the Earth bark Northern Tien Shan And adjacent territories // News NAN RK. Seriesgeological.-N 5.- Almaty, 2009-pp.59-67.
- [7] V.S Lyutikova., I.N. Litovchenko Pattern recognition technology (in identifying earthquake swarms) // MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH. Materials of reports XI International Conference of Young Scientists and Students. - Bishkek, 2019. - pp. 104-108.
- [8] V.S Lyutikova., I.N. Litovchenko Training algorithm for pattern recognition in solving practical problems // Robotics and Artificial Intelligence. - Proc. XI All-Russian scientific-technical conf . with int. uch. (Zheleznogorsk , December 14, 2019). - Zheleznogorsk, 2019. - [Electronic publication]. - pp.231-237.
- [9] V.S Lyutikova., I.N Litovchenko. Pattern recognition technology in detecting earthquake swarms//Knowledge-Ontology-Theory (ZONT-2019). - Mat.VII Int.conf ., 2019.-pp.233-237.
- [10] VS Lyutikova, I.N. Litovchenko Modern pattern recognition tools (by the example of earthquake swarms) Astana, 2023.- pp. 7-10.
- [11] N.M Panas., B.A Assinovskaya. Dynamic parameters of weak earthquakes of the eastern slope of the Baltic Shield//Russian Seismological Journal.-2022.-Vol.4, No. 4.- pp. 65-78. DOI : 10.33540/2686-7907/2022.4.05.- EDN : AFPGFJ
- [12] <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/>
- [13] S.B. Bychkov ENERGY OF EARTHQUAKES AND THE LAWS OF HYDRODYNAMICS/ [Electronic resource]: access mode - [http :// www . energiya-zemletryaseniy-i-zakony-gidrodinamiki.pdf](http://www.energiya-zemletryaseniy-i-zakony-gidrodinamiki.pdf)
- [14] V.S. Lyutikova, I.N. Litovchenko, N.B. Amirov About the question earthquakes and their aftershocks in the South East of Kazakhstan // XVII Global Science and innovations 2022: Central Asia International Scientific Practical Journal, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan.2022-PP.3-6.
- [15]A. G. Ivakhnenko "Polynomial theory of complex systems". *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics*, SMC-1(1):364378, 1971.
- [16]C. Naydanov, D. Palchunov and P. Sazonova, "Development of automated methods for the critical condition risk prevention, based on the analysis of the knowledge obtained from patient medical records," *2015 International Conference on Biomedical Engineering and Computational Technologies (SIBIRCON)*, Novosibirsk, Russia, 2015, pp. 33-38, doi: 10.1109/SIBIRCON.2015.7361845.